

Extended Abstract

Hyperbolic Elastic Metamaterials for Advanced Wave Propagation

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Modern requirements for optimal structural performance have driven the development of structures with unconventional designs and complex, multi-component materials. Drawing inspiration from nature but going far beyond it, artificial materials designed to compose such structures have led to the development of the so-called metamaterials. Their devised properties provided unprecedented problem-solving capabilities in acoustics, solid mechanics, thermal sciences, and optics (Maldovan, 2013; Hussein; Leamy; Ruzzene, 2014). In the vibration framework, many real-world applications in vibration control, cloaking, and frequency filtering (Gao *et al.*, 2022; Norris, 2008; Bukhari; Barry, 2019) benefit from the inherent metamaterial wave pass band and band gaps.

Among the vastness of metamaterial research, hyperbolic metamaterials have led to unique properties such as vibration localization, structural adaptation, super-resolution imaging, enhanced quantum effects, thermal hyper-conductivity (Smolyaninov, 2018; Jacob; Alekseyev; Narimanov, 2006; Ruzzene; Prodan; Prodan, 2021). At this point, the literature does not provide a clear distinction between hyperbolic behavior and hyperbolic geometric shapes, categorizing them broadly as hyperbolic metamaterials (Poddubny *et al.*, 2013; Maciejko; Rayan, 2021; Lee *et al.*, 2022). This raises several questions, e.g., how the hyperbolicity from topological behavior, which generates non-limited wave vector spaces, connects to the topology itself of hyperbolic geometric arrangements. Within this scope, this work addresses an initial investigation on the geometric arrangements of hyperbolic metamaterials.

Concerning metamaterials with hyperbolic geometric shapes, these form periodic lattices not restricted to the limited periodic arrangements of Euclidean geometry. To elucidate this, first consider the usual Euclidean regular and semi-regular tessellations, respectively composed of unique polygons symmetrically tiling the plane or by two or more convex regular polygons. Such polygons have to be met without gaps, which is only allowed by 11 configurations in the Euclidean plane, e.g., 4 squares or 3 hexagons at each vertex (Williams, 1979). On the other hand, the negative curvature from hyperbolic planes allows more polygons at each vertex, such as in Fig. 1, where the shown regular tessellation of 3 heptagons at each vertex over a hyperbolic surface is denoted by the Schläfli symbol $\{7, 3\}$ and represented by its Poincaré disk model. Notice that such a surface cannot be “unfolded” onto the Euclidean plane, that is, isometrically embedded into Euclidean spaces (Thurston, 1982; Urdapilleta *et al.*, 2015).

Figure 1: Hyperbolic surface $\{7, 3\}$ and its Poincaré disk representation

Knowing that the Poincaré disk model can represent entire hyperbolic spaces in a more convenient way than by its hyperbolic surfaces, consider the tessellation of four pentagons at each vertex shown in Fig. 2 (a). Notice this representation of a $\{5,4\}$ hyperbolic tessellation in the Poincaré disk is periodic in all directions in the hyperbolic space, although not fitting in the plane (Euclidean) geometry. Following Patino *et al.* (2025), the authors applied a conformal map $w(z) = (4/\pi) \arctan(z)$ for all points $z = x + iy$ in (a) to project disk slices into cells (b) arranged as a strip (c) of seven repeated cells.

Figure 2: $\{5,4\}$ hyperbolic tessellation

Figure 3 shows vibration mode shapes concentrating energy at the interior (a) and the boundary (b) regions of the strip centrally pinned in both extremities, built using COMSOL software and following Patino *et al.* (2025). This modal analysis reveals the existence of narrow vibration attenuation bands comparing the measurement points A and B along the strip by the FRFs (frequency response functions) in (c); meanwhile, a high density of localized out-of-plane interior and boundary modes is confirmed in (d). This localized vibration, interesting for harvesting and sensor placement, occurs at many closely spaced frequencies along the spectrum as a remarkable property of hyperbolic periodicity.

Figure 3: Localized vibration modes shapes and numerical spectrum of the $\{5,4\}$ hyperbolic strip

Aiming at expanding the presented hyperbolic studies, one can add periodic lumped masses to the strip of Fig. 2 (c) and redo the analysis to examine the changes in the dynamical behavior that this addition to the structure implies. Figure 4 is obtained from the modal analysis of the $\{5,4\}$ strip with lumped masses of 0.05 kg at the vertex of its central polygons, namely, to the first generation of mapped pentagons. Remarkably, the addition of periodic masses leads to intense vibration attenuation along the structure, which can be seen from the FRFs difference at the points A and B, and raises the concentration of boundary-localized modes, particularly due to higher displacements in the interior of the structure induced by the localized extra weight.

Figure 4: Numerical spectrum of the $\{5, 4\}$ hyperbolic strip with lumped masses

Studying the unit cell of Fig. 5 (a), one can compute the band diagrams (b) and (c) for the original structure and the structure with lumped masses, respectively. Here, the structure with added masses exhibits wider band gaps, highlighted by the shaded areas in the figure.

Figure 5: 3D $\{5, 4\}$ hyperbolic cell band gaps

Many original polygon configurations can still be explored to reach new wave phenomena. For instance, the study of the $\{4, 5\}$ hyperbolic disk from Fig. 6 (a), whose mapped cell (b) forms the strip (c), shows the FRFs (c) and the localization index (d), revealing a prominence of interior-localized modes. The localization of vibration modes at the structure's interior implies strong boundary isolation to vibration propagating to interconnected structures at the boundaries, thus suggesting potential innovative applications in vibration mitigation.

Figure 6: Tessellation and numerical spectrum of the $\{4, 5\}$ hyperbolic strip

References

- BUKHARI, M.; BARRY, O. Spectro-spatial analyses of a nonlinear metamaterial with multiple nonlinear local resonators. **Nonlinear Dynamics**, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, v. 99, n. 2, p. 1539–1560, nov. 2019. ISSN 1573-269X.
- GAO, N. *et al.* Acoustic Metamaterials for Noise Reduction: A Review. **Advanced Materials Technologies**, Wiley, v. 7, n. 6, jan. 2022. ISSN 2365-709X.
- HUSSEIN, M. I.; LEAMY, M. J.; RUZZENE, M. Dynamics of Phononic Materials and Structures: Historical Origins, Recent Progress, and Future Outlook. **Applied Mechanics Reviews**, ASME International, v. 66, n. 4, may 2014. ISSN 2379-0407.
- JACOB, Z.; ALEKSEYEV, L. V.; NARIMANOV, E. Optical Hyperlens: Far-field imaging beyond the diffraction limit. **Optics Express**, Optica Publishing Group, v. 14, n. 18, p. 8247, 2006. ISSN 1094-4087.
- LEE, D. *et al.* Hyperbolic metamaterials: fusing artificial structures to natural 2D materials. **eLight**, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, v. 2, n. 1, jan. 2022. ISSN 2662-8643.
- MACIEJKO, J.; RAYAN, S. Hyperbolic band theory. **Science Advances**, American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS), v. 7, n. 36, sep. 2021. ISSN 2375-2548.
- MALDOVAN, M. Sound and heat revolutions in phononics. **Nature**, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, v. 503, n. 7475, p. 209–217, nov. 2013. ISSN 1476-4687.
- NORRIS, A. N. Acoustic cloaking theory. **Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences**, The Royal Society, v. 464, n. 2097, p. 2411–2434, apr. 2008. ISSN 1471-2946.
- PATINO, N. H. *et al.* Elastic hyperbolic strip lattices. **Physical Review Applied**, American Physical Society (APS), may 2025. ISSN 2331-7019.
- PODDUBNY, A. *et al.* Hyperbolic metamaterials. **Nature Photonics**, Springer Science and Business Media LLC, v. 7, n. 12, p. 948–957, nov. 2013. ISSN 1749-4893.
- RUZZENE, M.; PRODAN, E.; PRODAN, C. Dynamics of elastic hyperbolic lattices. **Extreme Mechanics Letters**, Elsevier BV, v. 49, p. 101491, nov. 2021. ISSN 2352-4316.
- SMOLYANINOV, I. I. Hyperbolic metamaterial geometries and basic properties. In: **Hyperbolic Metamaterials**. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2018, (2053-2571). p. 1–1 to 1–6. ISBN 978-1-6817-4565-7. Available in: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/978-1-6817-4565-7ch1>.
- THURSTON, W. P. Three dimensional manifolds, Kleinian groups and hyperbolic geometry. **Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society**, American Mathematical Society (AMS), v. 6, n. 3, p. 357–382, may 1982. ISSN 0273-0979.
- URDAPILLETA, E. *et al.* Can rodents conceive hyperbolic spaces? **Journal of The Royal Society Interface**, The Royal Society, v. 12, n. 107, p. 20141214, jun. 2015. ISSN 1742-5662.
- WILLIAMS, R. **The geometrical foundation of natural structure**: A source book of design. New York: Dover Publ., 1979. ISBN 048623729X.